

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of methionine by pyridinium hydrobromide perbromide

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The oxidation of methionine (Met) by pyridinium hydrobromide perbromide (PHPB) has been studied in acetic acid-water (1 : 1) solutions. The oxidation reaction leads to the formation of the corresponding sulfoxide. The reaction is first order each in PHPB and Met. The reaction rates have been determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters calculated. A mechanism involving the formation of a halogen-sulfonium cation in the rate-determining step has been proposed.

Pyridinium hydrobromide perbromide (PHPB) has been extensively used in synthetic organic chemistry as a brominating and a dehydrating reagent^{1,2}. A number of reports on the mechanistic aspects of oxidations by PHPB are available in the literature³. However, the kinetics of oxidation of methionine by PHPB have not been reported. Methionine, a sulfur containing amino acid, is reported to behave differently from other amino acid towards many oxidants⁴ due to the presence of an electron-rich sulfur centre, which is easily oxidizable. In continuation of our earlier work on oxidation by PHPB, we report here the kinetics of oxidation of methionine by PHPB in acetic acid as solvent.

Results and Discussion

The reactions are first order with respect to PHPB. The individual kinetic runs show a first order dependence on [PHPB]. Further, the values of k_{obs} do not depend on the initial [PHPB]. The reaction rate increases linearly with an increase in the concentration of Met (Table 1).

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of methionine acid by PHPB at 293K

10^3 [PHPB] mol dm ⁻³	[Met] mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k_{obs}$, s ⁻¹
1.00	0.10	4.12
1.00	0.20	8.20
1.00	0.40	16.5
1.00	0.60	24.8
1.00	0.80	33.1
1.00	1.00	41.4
2.00	0.20	8.26
4.00	0.20	8.00
6.00	0.20	8.61
8.00	0.20	8.30
1.00	0.10	4.22 ^a

^aContained 0.005 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

The oxidation of methionine, in an atmosphere of nitrogen failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the reaction rate (Table 1). Thus a free radical mechanism is unlikely in this reaction. The addition of pyridinium hydrochloride or potassium bromide had no effect on the rate of oxidation of methionine (Table 2). The rates for the oxidation of hydroxy acids were obtained at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 3).

Table 2. Effect of pyridinium chloride/bromide ion on the rate of oxidation of methionine by PHPB

10^3 [PyHCl] or [Br ⁻] (mol dm ⁻³)	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1.0
$10^4 k_{obs}$ (s ⁻¹)					
PyHCl	4.20	3.94	4.57	4.00	4.46
Br ⁻	4.56	4.44	3.95	4.22	4.05

Table 3. Rate constants and activation parameters of the oxidation of methionine by PHPB

$10^4 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger
293	303	313	323 K	kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	J mol ⁻¹	kJ mol ⁻¹
4.14	9.35	19.1	39.7	56.5 ± 0.5	-117 ± 2	91.3 ± 0.4

In solutions, PHPB may undergo the following reactions,

The probable oxidizing species in a solution of PHPB are, therefore, PHPB itself, tribromide ion and molecular bromine. However, strict first order dependence on PHPB

Note

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